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Reconsidering the Ability of the Stimulus Unique Features to Capture
Attention: Evidence from Change Blindness and Visual Search Paradigms.

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Abstract

In Experiment 1 (change blindness), participants received either intermixed or blocked presentations of two visual stimuli that contained several common (X) and unique (A or B) features. On the critical trial after exposure, the stimulus AX was presented but included an unexpected visual event (a change in the size of a stimulus feature). We found that participants readily detected the change when it involved an A-unique feature that had been preexposed intermixed. However, if the change involved an A-unique feature preexposed in blocks, or an X-common feature (preexposed either intermixed or in blocks), the level of the detections considerably decreased. In Experiment 2, after either intermixed or blocked preexposure to AX and BX, all the participants were instructed to search for an unrelated visual target item. In the distractor condition, with no explicit instructions, the A-unique feature emerged in the search display during the development of the search task. In the control condition, the target was presented on its own during the entire task. The presence of the A-unique feature only produced a detrimental effect on search performance when the AX and BX had been preexposed intermixed. These results are discussed as indicative of the intermixed preexposure schedule enhancing the ability of the stimulus unique features to capture involuntary attention.

Key words: perceptual learning, intermixed-blocked, change blindness, visual search, stimulus salience.

Reconsidering the ability of the stimulus unique features to capture attention:

Evidence from change blindness and visual search paradigms.

Perceptual learning refers to the process by which experience with similar stimuli brings about changes in the way in which they are perceived. A well-documented example of this sort of learning is the demonstration that exposure to a pair of similar stimuli may enhance the readiness with which they are subsequently discriminated (for reviews, see Hall, 1991; Mitchell & Hall, 2014). It has been suggested that this enhancement of discrimination effect is mediated, at least in part, by changes in the amount of attention paid to various features of the stimuli. In particular, it has been proposed that experience with similar stimuli (e.g., AX and BX), especially under conditions promoting stimulus comparison, enhances attention to their unique features (A and B) and decreases attention to the common features (i.e., X) thus facilitating their differentiation. Although this is a relatively old proposal (e.g., Gibson, 1969; see also, e.g., Hall, 2003; Hall & Rodríguez, 2019; McLaren & Mackintosh, 2000), to date, not very much direct evidence has been offered supporting this attentional aspect of the phenomenon.

An important piece of this evidence is related to the so-called *intermixed-blocked effect*. This effect consists of the demonstration that stimulus discrimination is better enhanced by non-reinforced preexposure schedules that include frequent alternations of the stimuli (e.g., AX, BX, BX, AX, AX, BX...) than by schedules in which the same stimuli are presented equally often but in separate blocks of trials (e.g., AX, AX, AX... BX, BX,

BX...). The intermixed-blocked effect has been revealed as a robust phenomenon with both humans (e.g., Lavis & Mitchell, 2006; Mundy, Dwyer, & Honey, 2007; Rodríguez & Angulo, 2014) and non-human animals (e.g., Artigas, Sansa & Prados, 2006; Bennett & Mackintosh, 1999; Honey, Bateson & Horn, 1994; Rodríguez & Alonso, 2004; 2014; Symonds & Hall, 1995). Several experiments with humans in the visual domain have accompanied the evidence for this effect with data from the eye-tracker, and have revealed that participants show more fixations to the unique features of the stimuli when they have previously been preexposed intermixed than when they have been preexposed in blocks (e.g., Angulo, Alonso, Stassi, & Catena, 2019; Wang & Mitchell, 2011; Wang, Mitchell, Lavis, & Hall, 2012). These results are indicative that the intermixed preexposure brings an enhancement in the attention paid to the stimulus unique features. However, as several authors have noted (e.g., Jones and Dwyer, 2013; Mitchell & Hall, 2014), those data are not informative enough about some aspects of the mechanism, or mechanisms, responsible for those changes in attention.

A first question that remains to be elucidated is whether the intermixed schedule enhances the attention towards the unique features via bottom-up and/or top-down attentional mechanisms. According to a set of associative accounts of perceptual learning (e.g., Hall, 2003; McLaren & Mackintosh, 2000), the attentional changes underlying the intermixed-blocked effect are automatic and involuntary, and come mediated by another automatic and involuntary mechanism: the formation of associations. These accounts substantially differ in their specific proposals about how associative learning

and attention are related (we will turn into these differences in the General Discussion). But all of them concur into assume that the intermixed preexposure enhances the *salience* of the stimulus unique features (i.e., their ability to capture involuntary attention). The eye-tracker studies mentioned above did not provide direct evidence on this latter central assumption. In fact, in these studies (as in many other studies assessing the intermixed-blocked effect in the visual domain), participants are instructed to look for differences between stimuli during the preexposure phase. Under this sort of explicit instructions, any change in attention towards the stimulus features might be initiated by strategic choices by the participants rather than by any sort of automatic salience modulation. It has thus been proposed that the intermixed-blocked effect observed in this sort of human studies might be caused by different mechanisms to those involved in other instances of the effect observed with non-human animals (e.g., Mackintosh, 2009). Participants instructed to find differences between the stimuli would find it especially rewarding to detect the stimulus unique features, and the tendency to look to them would thus be strengthened by reinforcement during the preexposure. Although this sort of instructions would a priori highlight the relevance of the unique features in any schedule of the subsequent preexposure, there are grounds to expect that the tendency to look at the unique features would be established more readily during the intermixed preexposure. In this sort of studies, the intermixed schedule supplies rapid alternations between the stimuli thus facilitating the detection of their unique features and the opportunity for rewarding the orienting response to them. One of the aims of the present study was to clarify whether in the absence of this sort of explicit

instructions, evidence for the automatic and involuntary changes in attention that are predicted by the salience modulation accounts (e.g., Hall, 2003; McLaren & Mackintosh, 2000) can be found.

A second central aspect of these associative accounts of perceptual learning (e.g., Hall, 2003; McLaren & Mackintosh, 2000) is their elemental perspective. According to this view, any stimulus feature can be defined as a set of micro-characteristics, and the salience of all of them will be, in principle, variable. For example, if we consider that the unique feature *A* of a given visual stimulus *AX* is a red square presented in a given location, these accounts assume that intermixed preexposure to *AX* and *BX* might increase the salience of all of the microfeatures of *A* (i.e., the triangle shape, the red colour, and the location that this shape occupies). The studies that have shown a bigger number of fixations on the intermixed unique features (Angulo et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2012) do not directly support this assumption, since the unique features of the stimuli employed in their procedures were always presented in the same location. This procedural aspect makes thus possible that the bigger number of fixations observed on the intermixed unique features would be merely reflecting a tendency to look at (and/or to paying attention to) their location rather than to their content (e.g., their shape, colour etc.). Supporting this notion, some studies (e.g., Jones & Dwyer, 2013; Wang, Lavis, Hall, & Mitchell, 2012) have shown two related effects: 1) that the benefits of the intermixed preexposure on stimulus discrimination fade away when the location of the unique features is changed from preexposure to test, and 2) that, however, these benefits remain when novel unique features are

presented in the locations that the original unique features occupied during the preexposure. These two findings suggest that the location, but not the content, of the intermixed unique features has a strong ability for capturing voluntary and/or involuntary attention. At a first glance, this might be interpreted as challenging the salience modulation accounts. However, a reconciling explanation can be found if one examines the nature of the stimuli employed in this set of studies. These stimuli were coloured checkerboards, with a common pattern of many squares as the background (X), and with just a few adjacent squares of the same colour forming the unique features (e.g., A and B). Critically, the colour of the squares of the unique features was also used to colour other common squares of the stimuli. Similarly, although the shapes of the unique features were different to those shapes composing the common background, the right angles of the squares were obviously predominant in all the unique and common shapes. Therefore, among all the micro-characteristics (shape, colour, location...) that compose the unique features, only their location would be *entirely* unique. Accordingly, any effect of enhanced attention would be expected to be stronger on the location than on the content of this sort of unique features. So, when the unique features are presented in a different location on test (e.g., Jones & Dwyer, 2013), the superior attention to their previous locations might overshadow any similar but weaker effect of enhanced attention to their content. In short, according to this explanation, this set of previous studies might have not provided optimal conditions for detecting possible effects regarding the content of the unique features. It was the aim of the present study to look for more optimal conditions by using different stimuli and training conditions.

Summarizing, there is not yet clear and direct evidence supporting two central assumptions shared by a set of theories of perceptual learning (e.g., Gibson, 1969; Hall, 2003; Hall & Rodríguez, 2019; McLaren & Mackintosh, 2000): that the intermixed preexposure may enhance the attention to the stimulus unique features via involuntary and not goal-directed mechanisms, and that this mechanisms may affect to any the aspect of these features (i.e., their location and content). The experiments reported in the present study were designed in order to obtain this sort of evidence by using two attentional procedures: *change blindness* and *visual search*. A couple of previous studies (McLaren, Civile, Cooke, & McLaren, 2020; Suret & McLaren, 2001) already exploited these procedures in examining the mere effect of stimulus familiarity (i.e, they compared preexposed and non-preexposed conditions). Suret and McLaren exploited a change blindness procedure and McLaren et al. (2020) used a visual search paradigm. We however exploited these procedures to evaluate an intermixed-blocked comparison.

In Experiment 1, we used a *change blindness* procedure. Change blindness is a failure to notice changes in a visual scene or stimulus, when these are introduced during a brief interval of time in which the stimulus is masked or hidden (e.g., Simons & Ambinder, 2005; Simons & Rensink, 2005). A robust finding in the change blindness literature is that changes to attended objects are more detectable than changes to unattended objects (e.g., Kevin O'Reagan, Deubel, Clark, & Rensink, 2000), which opens the possibility to exploit this procedure as an attention tracker (e.g., Rodríguez-San Juan &

Rodríguez, 2017). We gave intermixed or blocked preexposure to two visual stimuli, and on a final critical trial we introduced a change in either a unique or a common feature of one of the stimuli. If intermixed preexposure enhances the ability of the stimulus unique features to capture attention, we expected to find better detection of the change (i.e., less change blindness) when this was introduced in a unique feature preexposed in an intermixed fashion. In Experiment 2, we used a procedure similar to that referred to as the *additional singleton paradigm* (e.g., Simons, 2000). In this paradigm, the performance in searching for a visual target item is delayed by the presence of an additional item that distracts attention. We exploited this procedure by testing the distracting ability of a previously exposed stimulus unique feature. If intermixed preexposure enhances the ability of the unique features to capture attention, we expected to find a greater delay in search performance (i.e., more evidence of distraction) after intermixed than after blocked preexposure.

EXPERIMENT 1

In our change blindness task, participants were first instructed to not do anything in particular when looking at a series of images presented in succession. For some participants (Group INT), the series consisted of intermixed presentations to a pair of visual stimuli (AX, BX, AX, BX, AX, BX...); for the remaining (Group BLK), the series consisted of the same number of presentations to those stimuli, but grouped in blocks of several trials (e.g., AX, AX, AX..., BX, BX, BX..., AX, AX, AX...). The stimulus AX was a red triangle and the stimulus BX was a blue square (see Figure 1). Both stimuli had a set of six symbols inside. Four of them were the same, had a

curvilinear form, and were present in both stimuli (i.e., they were x-common features). The two remaining symbols consisted of connected two straight lines, one horizontal and one vertical. For one symbol, the two lines connected at the top of the vertical line, and for the other symbol, the lines connected in the middle of the vertical line. One of these two remaining symbols was also present in both stimuli and was the *target common feature*. The other symbol had a peculiarity in each stimulus which was the orientation of its horizontal line, pointing to the left in the case of the triangle and pointing to the right in the case of the circle. These two symbols were used as target unique and common features, and their location in the stimuli, was counterbalanced across participants.

Immediately after the preexposure, the stimulus AX (i.e., the red triangle) was presented two additional times, though as these were additional trials of the preexposure stage. On the second additional trial (the critical trial) all the participants received with no explicit warning a modified version of AX. Thus, in contrast with other change blindness procedures, our participants were not aware that a change was to be introduced before this happened. The unexpected change was a reduction of 50% in the size of the horizontal line of one of the target symbols inside the triangle. For some participants in each preexposure condition, the change was introduced in the target common feature (AX') (Group INT-Common and Group BLK-Common) and for the remainder it was introduced in the target distinctive feature (A'X) (Group INT-Unique and Group BLK-Unique). Subsequently, all the participants were required to describe any detail out of the normal that they might have noticed

in this latest trial of the task. Participants who described the shortening of the bar were considered to have offered a right answer. Participants who reported nothing unexpected, or reported something that did not occur (anything different to the shortening of the line) were considered to have suffered change blindness. If intermixed preexposure to AX and BX enhances the ability of their unique features (A and B) to capture attention, the change should be more readily detected in Group INT-Unique than in the remaining groups. A clear feature effect (unique vs. common) should be observed in the intermixed condition (with better performance in Group INT-Unique than in Group-Common), and perhaps an attenuation of this effect might be observed in the blocked condition (with a much less clear superiority of Group BLK-Unique over Group BLK-Common).

Method

Participants

Sample size was determined based on an a priori power analysis (Faul, Erdfelder, Lang, & Buchner, 2007), to detect an expected medium effect ($w = .3$) for the interaction between the preexposure schedule (intermixed vs. blocked) and the stimulus feature type (unique vs. common), when using a log-linear analysis, $\alpha = .05$ (two-tailed), with a power of .8 as recommended by Cohen (1988). This analysis revealed that a total sample size of $N = 133$ was required. We approximated this number, using a slightly smaller sample of $N = 128$, to maintain equal cell sizes ($n = 32$). Importantly, post hoc power analysis (see Section Results and Discussion) revealed that the study was sufficiently powered.

The participants were 128 students (80 female; mean age = 19.14 years, range: 18-33) from the University of the Basque Country who agreed to participate after being informed that they would take part in an experiment involving cognitive tasks. All of them had normal or corrected-to-normal vision. The Research Ethics Committee of the University of the Basque Country (CEISH) approved the experimental protocol. Participants were split between, and randomly assigned to the INT-Unique (n = 32), INT-Common (n = 32), BLK-Unique (n=32), and BLK-Common (n = 32) groups.

Apparatus and stimuli

The participants were tested individually, sitting at approximately 50 cm from the 17-inch screen of a standard PC.

Figure 1 shows the two complex visual stimuli used in the exposure phase of this experiment. Each of these stimuli had two salient distinctive features: the geometric shape (circle vs. triangle) and the colour of the shape (red vs. blue). Each shape contained inside a 3 x 2 matrix of symbols in black colour. Four of the six symbols (those in the first and third column of the matrix) were identical, had a curvilinear shape, and were present in the two stimuli (i.e., they were common features shared by the stimuli). The two remaining symbols were created by connecting a vertical bar with a shorter horizontal bar: in one symbol the bars connected at the top of the vertical bar, and in the other connected in the middle of the vertical bar. For half of the participants in each group, one of these symbols was the target unique feature and the other was the target common feature, and for the remainder these assignments were reversed. The symbol assigned as the target

common feature was identically present in the two stimuli, with the horizontal bar pointing to the left. However, in the symbol assigned as the target unique feature, the horizontal bar was pointing to the left when it was presented in the triangle and was pointing to the right when it was presented in the circle. The location of the target symbols (top or bottom row in the second column of the 3 x 2 matrix) was also fully counterbalanced across participants. We can thus describe these two stimuli as AX and BX, where A would be the set of unique features of the “triangle” stimulus (its shape, the red colour of the contour, and the target unique feature pointing to the left), B would be the set of unique features of the “circle” stimulus (its shape, the blue colour of its contour, and the target unique feature pointing to the right), and X would be the remaining features of the stimuli, primarily the set of 5 symbols presented inside both shapes.

Procedure

Participants initially received the following on-screen instructions (in Spanish): *Please, whenever you are ready press the spacebar of the keyboard to start. The automatic presentation of a sequence of images then will begin. You don't have to do anything in particular when looking at them.* The preexposure task comprised 64 trials with 32 exposures to each of the stimuli. On each trial, the corresponding stimulus appeared on a white background for 2 s. The presentation of a white screen for 1 s. was intercalated between trials. For the participants in the intermixed condition (Groups INT-Unique, INT-Common), the order of stimulus presentations, repeated four times, was as follows: cttc tcct tcct cttc (where t = triangle and c

= circle). For **half of the participants** in the blocked condition (Groups BLK-Unique, BLK-Common), the order of stimulus presentations, repeated two times, was as follows: tttt tttt tttt tttt cccc cccc cccc cccc (where t = triangle and c = circle). **For the remaining participants in these groups, the order of stimulus presentations, repeated two times was this: cccc cccc cccc cccc tttt tttt tttt.**

For all the participants, two additional exposures to the triangle stimulus followed the preexposure stage (tt'). The second of these presentations was used as the critical trial. On this trial, the change to be noticed was a reduction of the 50% in the size of the critical horizontal bar (Figure 1 shows an instance of the modified stimuli presented on the critical trial). For participants in the condition Unique (Groups INT-Unique and BLK-Unique), the reduced horizontal bar was part of the target unique feature. For participants in the condition Common (Groups INT-Common and BLK-Common), the reduced horizontal bar was part of the target common feature.

Immediately after the critical trial, participants were presented with the following question that appeared (in Spanish) on the screen “*On this latter trial, did you see anything peculiar with respect to other previous trials? If your answer is yes, please describe what you saw into a text field*”. Participants had 30 seconds to give their responses.

Data treatment and analysis

Only the participants who described the shortening of the bar were considered to have offered a right answer. Participants who reported nothing unexpected (or reported something that did not occur, that is, anything

different to the shortening of a bar) were considered to have suffered change blindness. Accuracy of the test responses was coded by two independent raters who were blind to the group assignment and to the hypotheses of the present study. The inter-rater reliability was perfect (the Cohen's Kappa value was $k = 1.00$, $p < .001$). Chi-square tests and hierarchical log-linear analyses were used to examine categorical data. Cramer's phi coefficient (ϕ) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were also calculated to examine effect sizes. The level of statistical significance was defined as an alpha less than .05. All analyses were two-tailed.

Results and Discussion

Figure 2 shows the percentages of detections of the unexpected change in the different groups of Experiment 1. It is apparent from the figure that after intermixed preexposure, the change was more readily detected when it was introduced in the target unique symbol (Group INT-Unique) than when it was introduced in the target common symbol (Group INT-Common); however, after blocked preexposure the change was equally roughly detected when it was introduced in either of the two target symbols (i.e., there were not differences between the Groups BLK-Unique and BLK-Common). Statistical analyses confirmed all these impressions. A hierarchical log-linear analysis exploring the effects of schedule of exposure (INT vs. BLK), modified feature (Unique vs. Common), and accuracy (correct vs. incorrect answers) indicated that the three-way interaction was significant, $\chi^2(4) = 17.77$, $p < .005$, $\phi = .37$, 95% CI = [0.15, 0.51]. A post hoc power calculation revealed a power of 94% for this interaction, indicating that the study was sufficiently powered. This

interaction is mainly caused by a relatively higher number of correct detections in Group INT-Unique. Further analyses in order to clarify the source of this interaction showed better test performance in Group INT-Unique than in groups INT-Common, $\chi^2(1) = 14.19$, $p < .001$, $\varphi = .47$, 95% CI = [0.23, 0.72], BLK-Unique, $\chi^2(1) = 7.57$, $p = .006$, $\varphi = .34$, 95% CI = [0.09, 0.58], and BLK-Common, $\chi^2(1) = 10.57$, $p = .0011$, $\varphi = .41$, 95% CI = [0.16, 0.65]. The feature effect found in the intermixed condition (the better performance of Group INT-Unique over Group INT-Common) did not result significant in the blocked condition, $\chi^2(1) = 0.29$, $p = .589$, $\varphi = .07$. Neither the schedule effect in the common feature condition (i.e., the comparison between the Group INT-Common and the Group BLK-Common), $\chi^2(1) = 0.33$, $p = .5637$, $\varphi = .07$, either the remaining comparison between the groups INT-Common and BLK Unique, $\chi^2(1) = 1.24$, $p = .266$, $\varphi = .14$, were significant.

The present pattern of results is consistent with the notion that intermixed stimulus preexposure brings about an increase in the attention paid to the unique stimulus features. It is important to note that the significant difference observed between the performance of the groups INT-Unique and INT-Common helps to discard some alternative explanations. For example, that the superior performance showed by Group INT-Unique was merely due to a general effect of the intermixed schedule in maintaining the motivation and/or the arousal of the participants.

This new evidence adds to that from previous studies, and extends it in several respects. On the one hand, it includes performance to the unique and

common features (unlike the previous studies using eye-tracking techniques, that did not offer information about the performance to the common features, e.g., Angulo et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2011). On the other hand, the attentional component of the intermixed-blocked effect is highlighted. It is known that the locus of fixation does not necessarily coincide always with the locus of attention (e.g., Henderson, 1992). The eye-tracking techniques employed in the previous studies could thus be just indicating that participants are *looking at* the content and/or the location of the unique features rather than being paying attention to them. Assessment of the ability of the participants to notice the presence of an unexpected change ensures monitoring of their processing of the stimulus features. The fact that the ability to detect this sort of change was superior in Group INT-Unique suggests that participants in the intermixed condition showed a better stimulus processing of the unique feature. It must be acknowledged, however, that our pattern of results might be still consistent with the existence of a location bias in the intermixed condition (e.g., Jones and Dwyer 2013). According to this explanation, all the participants in this condition would have acquired a bias to look at, and/or to pay attention, to the place occupied by the unique features. So, participants in Group INT-Unique would have showed superior performance on test just because they were looking at the place in which the change occurred, not because their attention would have been more strongly captured by the content of that feature. So, it is fair to admit that the present results are suggestive, but not decisive, in providing evidence for the notion that the salience of the unique features is enhanced by intermixed preexposure.

An additional interesting aspect of the present results is the finding of an intermixed-blocked effect in the absence of instructions encouraging the participants to look for differences between the preexposed stimuli. This might be taken as evidence that the attentional changes that are involved in this sort of human intermixed-blocked effect are, at least in part, caused by involuntary mechanisms. However, this suggestion must be taken with caution since it is true that our participants could have guessed, from the nature of the preexposure training, that the goal of the experiment was finding differences between the stimuli, and paying attention to them. So, it is still possible that our results would be entirely caused by top-down controlled attentional mechanisms. In short, we still have two pending questions on the table: 1) did the participants from Group INT-Unique more readily detect the change because they were paying attention to a given location and/or because they were paying attention to the content of the features that occupy that place? And, 2) why were they paying more attention to that content and/or place? Was it because they had some strategy (it was a goal-directed sort of attention)? Or was it because the stimulus unique features acquired the ability to capture their attention? We attempted to offer more decisive answers to these questions in the following experiment.

EXPERIMENT 2

In this experiment we made use of the procedure referred to as the *additional singleton paradigm* (e.g., Simons, 2000). It is a sort of visual search task in which participants are instructed to search for a specific target item. Critically, in the search display, the target is presented along with another

item, a distractor (the added singleton), that is completely unrelated to the target. Experiments using this sort of task typically show that search performance is slower when an additional salient distractor is present, relative to when no distractor is present. We exploited this procedure in the following way. Two experimental conditions received the same preexposure schedules tested in Experiment 1: intermixed or blocked preexposure to the same complex stimuli used in the previous experiment. After this training, participants were instructed to use the mouse of the computer to click, as fast as possible, on a given target that would appear in an unpredictable location. This target (the drawing of an apple; see Figure 3) was presented to all the participants along with the instructions. When the participants agreed to start the experiment, a countdown of 5 seconds started; this helped to fix the gaze of the participants at the centre of the screen. For all the participants, immediately after this countdown, the target item (i.e., the apple) was presented in a given location of the searching display. For half of the participants in each of the preexposure conditions (Group INT-distractor and Group BLK-distractor), 300 msec after that the target apple was presented, the stimulus unique feature of AX also emerged but in a different location. That is, for these participants, the unique stimulus feature-A served as the distractor. For the other half of the participants in each preexposure condition (Group INT-CTRL and Group BLK-CTRL), the apple was presented alone in the search display, during the entire task. We expected to observe longer search times for groups exposed to the distractor during the task. In addition, if intermixed preexposure enhances the ability of the stimulus unique features to capture attention, we expected to observe that the presence of the unique

feature would interfere to a greater extent in search performance after intermixed than after blocked preexposure. Critically, if these results were to be found, they could not be attributed to a location bias, since the unique feature was going to emerge at an unpredictable location, different to that at which it was presented during the preexposure. In addition, it would be difficult to ascribe the expected pattern of results to any goal-directed attentional mechanism since in the present task, the (top-down) goal of the participant (i.e., finding the apple and clicking on it) is in opposition with paying attention to the unique feature that serves as a distractor.

Method

Participants, apparatus, and materials

Ninety-six students (62 female; mean age = 19.56 years, range: 18-47) from the University of the Basque Country agreed to participate after being informed that they would take part in an experiment involving cognitive tasks. All of them had normal or corrected-to-normal vision. The Research Ethics Committee of the University of the Basque Country (CEISH) approved the experimental protocol. **The sample size was determined by a power analysis of pilot data.** Participants were split between, and randomly assigned to the INT-Distractor (n = 24), INT-CTRL (n = 24), BLK-Distractor (n=24), and BLK-CTRL (n = 24) groups.

Procedure.

The initial preexposure phase was almost identical to the stimulus presentations described for the intermixed and blocked conditions in

Experiment 1. The only difference was that in the present experiment the last additional presentation of AX (the triangle) did not include any modification of the stimulus features. Immediately after the preexposure ended, participants received the following on-screen instructions (in Spanish; see Figure 3): *In order to perform the following task, you will have to use the mouse of the computer. This image is going to be presented (the image of the apple was then presented) and you must mark its location by clicking on it with the cursor of the mouse. You have to try to do it AS FAST AS POSSIBLE. Press the green button whenever you will be ready to start.* When participants pressed the button, a countdown of 5 seconds started in which the following text (in Spanish) was presented at the centre of the screen: *We start on 5 (4, 3, 2, 1...) seconds.* Immediately after this period of time, for all the participants, the apple was presented in a given location (coordinates: $x=90$, $y=90$). For participants in groups INT-Distractor and BLK-Distractor, 300 msec after that the apple was presented, the symbol that was used as the unique feature of the triangle (A) emerged in a different location (coordinates: $x=-40$, $y=30$). For participants in groups INT-CTRL and BLK-CTRL, however, the target item (the apple) was presented alone, during the entire task.

Data treatment and analysis

Individual search times were registered. **Three outliers were removed: one in each of the following groups: INT-Distractor, BLK-Distractor and BLK-Ctrl. Since** Levene's test indicated significant heterogeneity of variances among the groups, **a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test was used to determine overall differences among groups. The Mann-Whitney test was**

used as post-hoc, and Bonferroni correction was considered. The level of statistical significance was defined as an alpha less than .05. All analyses were two-tailed.

Results and Discussion

Figure 4 shows the individual (black points) and mean (red points) search times (in sec) of Experiment 2. It is apparent from the figure that Group INT-Distractor took longer to complete the task, and showed a greater diversity, than the remaining groups, which did not differ appreciably from each other in any of these regards.

A mean-based Levene test showed that variances were not homogeneous, $F(3, 89) = 7.25, p < 0.001$. Accordingly, an independent-sample Kruskal-Wallis test was used, and revealed a significant effect of group $\chi^2(3) = 30.66, p < .001$. Bonferroni corrected Mann-Whitney post-hoc comparisons showed the following results: Group INT-distractor significantly differed from groups INT-Ctrl ($p < 0.001$), BLK-Distractor ($p = 0.005$), and BLK-Ctrl, ($p < 0.001$). Group BLK-distractor did not significantly differed from either Group BLK-Ctrl ($p = 0.09$) or Group INT-Ctrl ($p = 1$), and Group BLK-Ctrl did not significantly differed from Group INT-Ctrl ($p = 1$). These results support the notion that intermixed preexposure enhances the ability of the content of the unique features to capture involuntary attention. Next, we will take into consideration the implications of these results for the field of perceptual learning.

General Discussion

The intermixed-blocked effect is certainly a phenomenon around which the theoretical debate about the mechanisms for perceptual learning has more intensely revolved during the latter decades. Despite the intense research that has been dedicated to this issue in order to clarify the nature of these mechanisms, there are some questions that have remained unsolved. In the present study, we have attempted to contribute to elucidate two of these questions: whether intermixed preexposure enhances the ability of the *content* of the unique features to capture attention, and whether the mechanisms involved in this attentional effect are involuntary. Several studies *on the beguining of the century* (e.g., Blair & Hall, 2003; Mondragón & Hall, 2002; Rodríguez & Alonso, 2004) have *already* tested these matters and they seemed to bring clear, but to some extent indirect, evidence about the notion that the intermixed preexposure enhances the salience of the unique features. Given the nature of these studies (that employed rats as subjects and flavors as stimuli), the answers to the posed questions undoubtedly seemed to be “yes”. We thought that learned changes in salience must be caused by *involuntary* mechanisms because the rats in these experiments obviously were not instructed in looking for differences. And the debate about the importance of the content/location of the unique features was not even considered. First, because it would have been peculiar to have suggested that establishing the difference between the location and the content of the salty flavor could be relevant, and second, because we were aware of several instances of non-human perceptual learning in the visual domain (e.g., Gibson & Walk, 1956). The theoretical debate was thus understandably centred on

the nature of the involuntary associative and attentional mechanisms supposedly responsible for perceptual learning (e.g., Gibson, 1969; Hall, 1991; 2003; McLaren, Kaye, & Mackintosh, 1989). The field turned towards the questions considered in the present study when we started to discuss certain instances of the intermixed-blocked effect found in human studies using visual stimuli (e.g., Lavis & Mitchell, 2006). Why did these questions then become relevant? My argument is as follows.

The experimental procedures that we started to develop for studying visual perceptual learning in humans were (and keep being) very different to those with animals in many aspects. One important difference is the length of the experiments: human experiments are much shorter. In the pioneer study by Gibson and Walk (1956), for example, rats received presentations to the target visual stimuli during several weeks, but in an experiment in the human visual domain, participants are exposed to the stimuli just for a few minutes. It is not so surprising then, that in order to obtain some improvement on the performance of quite difficult visual discriminations (e.g., Lavis & Mitchell, 2006), participants need some help, some contribution of an extra factor: the instructions, that probably enhance their sustained attention and their intrinsic motivation at helping to see the task as a challenge with a clear goal: finding differences between stimuli (e.g., Angulo & Alonso, 2012; Navarro, Arriola, & Alonso, 2016; Recio, Iliescu, Mingorance, Bergés, Hall, & de Brugada, 2016). The obvious problem is that the introduction of these extra factors might be distorting the phenomenon in which we were interested when we began our research. When introducing explicit instructions to look for differences among the stimuli, we are not just speeding up the same mechanisms present in the

genuine non-reinforced preexposure, but we are promoting other different mechanisms and, perhaps, also the appearance of other sorts of improving effects in discriminative performance (although we still label them as intermixed-blocked, or perceptual learning, effects). Several challenges emerge here. One interesting challenge is understanding how instructed learning and perceptual learning interact. Another sort of challenge, which is the one that we accepted in the present study, is to persist in looking for more optimal and simple experimental arrangements that will allow us to study in the human visual domain, the predictions about involuntary attentional effects derived from our “classic” perceptual learning accounts (e.g., Gibson, 1969; Hall, 2003; McLaren & Mackintosh, 2000). In the experiments reported here, we attempted to achieve this by appealing to two attentional paradigms: change blindness (Experiment 1) and a visual search task (Experiment 2). In Experiment 1, we confirmed that a change blindness task can be successfully exploited as an attention tracker in order to evaluate learned changes in attention during the stimulus preexposure (Rodríguez-San Juan & Rodríguez, 2017). We found that participants readily noticed the presence of a change when it was introduced in a unique stimulus feature that had been preexposed intermixed. However, if the change was introduced in a unique feature preexposed in blocks, or in a common feature (preexposed either intermixed or in blocks), the level of detections was less. Unlike other previous studies, in this experiment, the participants were not instructed to look for differences between the stimuli during the preexposure. So, the finding of these feature (unique vs. common) and preexposure schedule (intermixed vs. blocked) effects are quite relevant. Why did we have such a success with a quite short

stimulus preexposure and in the absence of explicit instructions? Probably because our stimuli were much simpler, and therefore more easily distinguishable, than those used in previous studies (e.g., the colour checkerboards used in many studies). Reducing the general level of difficulty for establishing what stimulus features are unique and common might have facilitated any attentional process involving them. Our results were consistent with the notion that intermixed preexposure enhanced the ability of the content of the unique features to capture attention, but they were also consistent with the existence of a location bias. Participants from the intermixed condition could have developed during the preexposure a tendency to look at the fixed place occupied by the unique features, and this might have helped them to notice the introduced change on the critical trial. Experiment 2 helped us to disentangle the possible effects based on the location and the content of the unique features. In this experiment, after the preexposure training, the participants were instructed to perform a task in which they had to search a visual target item that was unrelated to the stimuli to which they had been preexposed. For half of the participants (the distractor condition), with no explicit advice, a unique feature of the preexposed stimuli emerged in the search display during the development of the task. For the remaining participants (the control condition), the target item was presented on its own during the entire task. The presence of the unique feature produced a detrimental effect on the search performance when the stimuli had been preexposed intermixed but not when the stimuli had been preexposed in blocks. These results indicate that intermixed preexposure enhanced the salience of the content of the unique features, and that this effect was

independent from their location. Based on this direct evidence, we can offer positive answers to the two questions posed in the Introduction: intermixed preexposure does enhance the ability of the content of the stimulus features to capture attention, and this attentional effect does not seem to be goal-directed. The results from our study thus come to confirm that the principles proposed by those theories that explain perceptual learning in terms of learned changes in attention (e.g., Gibson, 1969; Hall, 2003; Hall & Rodríguez, 2017; McLaren & Mackintosh, 2000) also may extend to the human visual domain.

Before finishing, we must to consider some previous results that seem to enter into contradiction with ours. It is the case of some aspects of the results provided by Jones and Dwyer (2013). The aim of their study was similar to that of ours: ascertaining the possible separate contributions of the content (i.e., the shape, size, colour, etc.) and the location of the unique features in the capturing of attention. Unlike the present experiment, Jones and Dwyer (2013) instructed to the participants to look for differences between the preexposed stimuli, and used quite complex stimuli (colour checkerboards similar to those used by Lavis & Mitchell, 2006). Their experimental strategy was quite different as well. They examined the effect of giving intermixed preexposure to certain stimuli (e.g., AX and BX) and testing subsequently the ability to discriminate between another stimuli that contained modified versions of the trained unique features (e.g., A'X and B'X). They did not include the common blocked control condition. They found good transfer of the enhanced discrimination effect when the unique features of the novel

test stimuli (e.g., A' and B') had the same location but different content with respect to the trained unique features. This result is consistent with the notion that intermixed preexposure enhances (involuntarily or not) the attention paid to the location of the unique feature. On test, people would have been paying attention to the same location where they usually found the old unique features during training. This location bias would have helped them to readily find the new unique features and thus to sort perfectly out the new discrimination. This result, however, does not help to clarify whether this change in attention is accompanied by a parallel enhancing of attention towards the content of the intermixed unique features. In order to clarify this point, Jones and Dwyer (2013) also assessed the ability to discriminate between novel test stimuli whose modified unique features (e.g., A' and B') had the same content but different location with respect to the trained unique features (A and B). Under these conditions, no transfer of enhanced discrimination was found, which was interpreted as challenging the idea that, in this sort of visual procedure, the intermixed preexposure brought a genuine enhancement of the salience of the unique features. These results are in apparent contradiction with our findings of Experiment 2. If intermixed preexposure enhances the salience of the content of the unique features, the participants of their study should have been able to detect them readily, even in a different location, thus facilitating the discrimination of the test stimuli. Is it possible to reconcile the results of Jones and Dwyer (2013) with ours? We believe that an account in terms of generalization decrement can make it. As it was mentioned before, the stimuli used by Jones Dwyer (2013) consisted of a 20 x 20 square checkerboard, and were created from a common structure

(the X element) in which 156 bright coloured squares (e.g., blue, green, purple, red or yellow) were mixed with 244 gray squares. The unique features (e.g., A and B) were added by changing the colour of six adjacent blocks of gray squares (of the X element) to two of the brighter colours. There was not an explicit indication of the boundaries of the unique features (for example, these boundaries were not marked with a border). The location of the squares conforming the common (X) and unique features (A and B) remained constant across the preexposure training. So, it is plausible that the perception of the content of the unique features (for example, their shape) would have been affected not only by the six squares that were objectively defined by the researchers as the “unique feature”, but also by the stable presence of their neighbour squares (which were objectively a part of the X element) across the preexposure training (specially, for example, for those cases in which some of these neighbour squares had the same colour than the actual *unique* squares). Given that the background used as X element was not uniform, when the location of the content of the unique features was modified on test, their neighbour squares were changed as well. It is, therefore, possible that these new neighbours generated a different perception of the unique features, thus attenuating the expression of any salience effect related to what was perceived during the preexposure. This generalization decrement would have not been relevant in our Experiment 2, since our stimulus unique features (that consisted of connected black straight lines, and were presented in a white background during the preexposure) would have been readily recognized when they were presented on another location (but still in the same white background) during the visual search task. This account weakens

the challenging interpretation of the results from Jones and Dwyer (2013), but it has to be a matter of future research to empirically test it. For example, it would be interesting to exploit the design of the present Experiment 2 but with checkerboard stimuli. And, it seems also worthy to replicate the designs of Jones and Dwyer (2013) but trying to equate the content of the neighbour squares of the unique features during both the preexposure and the test, thus minimizing the possible contribution of generalization decrement.

To summarize, the present study has contributed to the advance in the study of perceptual learning in two different ways: first, by expanding the number of known experimental procedures (change blindness and visual search task) useful for investigating issues related to this phenomenon. And second, by clarifying that, also in the human visual domain, intermixed preexposure enhances the salience of the stimulus content of the unique features (i.e., enhance their ability to capture involuntary attention).

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Training stimuli:

Test stimuli:

Figure 1: Examples of training and test (modified) stimuli used in Experiment 1.

Figure 2. Percentages of detections on the critical trial of Experiment 1.

Participants in the Intermixed condition received 32 intermixed presentations of each of the two stimuli (see Figure 1) during the initial training (AX, BX, AX, BX...); participants in the Blocked condition received the same number of stimulus presentations, but distributed in 4 blocks of 16 trials with the same stimulus (AX, AX, AX...BX, BX, BX...AX, AX, AX...BX, BX, BX...). All the participants received two additional trials: one with AX, and the second with a modified version of AX (the critical trial). For participants in the condition Unique, the modification consisted of the presentation of an unexpected change in the A unique stimulus feature (see Figure 1); for participants in Group Common, the modification consisted of an equivalent change but in an X common stimulus feature (see Figure 1).

Figure 3: Schematic representation of the different trial structures used in the visual search task of Experiment 2, for the Distractor and Control conditions.

Figure 4. Mean search times (in sec) for each of the four groups of Experiment 2. Participants in the Intermixed condition received 32 intermixed presentations of each of the two stimuli (see Figure 1) during the initial training (AX, BX, AX, BX...); participants in the Blocked condition received the same number of stimulus presentations, but distributed in 4 blocks of 16 trials with the same stimulus (AX, AX, AX...BX, BX, BX...AX, AX, AX...BX, BX, BX...). All the participants received two additional trials with AX. After this training, participants were instructed to perform a visual search task (on a single trial), by locating with the mouse of the computer a target stimulus (see Figure 3). For participants in the Distractor condition, 300 msec after the target was presented, the unique feature A (the distractor) also emerged but in a different location. For participants in the Control condition, the target was presented alone during the entire task (see Figure 3). Vertical bars represent the standard errors of the mean (SEMs).